

management was conducted with transplanted Jaya rice on Tarai soil in the lowlands of Uttar Pradesh, India, during the 1977-78 wet season. Total nitrogen used was 60 kg/ha as ordinary urea, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea-enriched farmyard manure (FYM), urea incubated with soil, and pellet application of urea incubated with soil. Single superphosphate and muriate of potash at 40 kg P₂O₅/ha and 25 kg K₂O/ha were basally applied to all plots.

Differences in grain yield due to source and timing of N application were significant. Nitrogen use was most efficient with SCU broadcast as a single application and incorporated into the soil before transplanting (see table).

Effect of timing of application and source of nitrogen (N) on grain yield of rice. Pantnagar, India.

Planting	N application (kg/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)
	Early tillering	Late tillering	Panicle initiation	
0	0	0	0	4.9
60	0	0	0	6.4
15	15	15	15	6.9
0	30	0	30	6.4
0	20	20	20	6.5
30 ^a	15 ^a	0	15 ^a	6.5
30 ^b	15 ^b	0	15 ^b	6.4
60 ^c	0	0	0	7.1
30 ^c	15	0	15	7.0
30 ^d	15 ^d	0	15 ^d	6.3

S.E m± 0.2

CD at 5% 0.6

CV (%) 7

^a Urea incubated with soil. ^b Pellet application of urea incubated with soil. ^c Sulfur-coated urea.

^d Urea-enriched farmyard manure.

Fertilizer and weed management of aus rice in Bangladesh

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Inadequate weed and fertilizer management hampers aus (monsoon) rice production in Bangladesh.

A 1979 experiment in the BRRZ

project area used the improved variety Chandina under farmer conditions to determine: 1) the yield gap between the potential and the farmer's actual yields, 2) the effectiveness of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control on yield, and 3) the economics of alternative practices. The design was complete factorial in a randomized complete block, with three applications, each with nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control. The crops were grown with supplementary irrigation.

Yield with the farmer's practices (2.6 t/ha) and potential yield (4.3 t/ha) showed a gap of 1.7 t/ha (see table). The use of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed control bridged the gap by 0.7, 0.6, and 0.7 t/ha, respectively. The change brought in a net income of US\$415/ha. The benefit-cost ratio for the extra investment ranged from 5.3 to 16.4, depending on the treatment combinations. ■

Agroeconomics of nitrogen, sulfur, and weed management over farmer's levels in BRRZ cropping systems research site at Salna, Bangladesh, 1979 aus.

Treatment ^a			Av yield (t/ha)	Yield difference from farmers' level (kg/ha)	Value of yield difference (US\$/ha)	Cost of H inputs (US\$/ha)	Added profit over farmer's treatment (US\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Nitrogen	Sulfur	Weeding frequency						
F(54 kg/ha)	F(0)	F(zero)	2.6	—	—	—	—	—
F	F	H(3)	3.0	401	106.93	7.87	99.06	12.6
F	H(34 kg/ha)	F	3.1	440	117.33	14.53	102.80	7.1
F	H	H	3.2	532	141.86	22.40	119.47	5.3
H(80 kg/ha)	F	F	3.1	453	120.80	7.20	113.60	15.8
H	F	H	3.3	686	182.93	15.07	167.87	11.1
H	H	F	4.1	1419	378.40	21.73	356.67	16.4
H	H	H	4.3	1669	445.06	29.60	415.47	14.0

^a F = farmer's level of management (traditional system), H = improved management (improved variety).

Modified urea materials and nitrogen efficiency in wetland rice

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The growth and yield of wetland rice

depend on the availability and use of nitrogen at the various physiological stages of the crop. Split application, placement, and controlled release are the three major approaches to increasing nitrogen efficiency in wetland rice. Five seasons of experimentation at Mandya have shown that the basal application of nitrogen in mudballs, paper capsules, and

as supergranules and sulfur-coated urea is superior to split application.

In a replicated trial conducted in the summer of 1979 under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), basal application of several modified urea materials was compared with basal and split applications of prilled urea. Granulated compost and super-